

Rate-distortion/complexity analysis of video compression with capability beyond HEVC

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Abstract ITU-T Video Coding Expert Group (VCEG) and ISO/IEC Moving Picture Expert Group (MPEG) are studying the potential need for standardization of the future video coding technology with a compression capability that significantly exceeds that of the current High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard, including its current extensions. Both groups are working together on this exploration activity in a collaboration effort known as Joint Video Exploration Team (JVET) to evaluate compression technology designs proposed by their experts in this area. This paper describes the coding features that are under coordinated test model study by the JVET, and presents a rate-distortion/complexity analysis to study their real capabilities. Experimental results show that the new model achieves 25% bitrate reduction, but at a cost of extremely high computational complexity (11×) with respect to HEVC.

Keywords HEVC · JEM · Evaluation · Computational cost

1 Introduction

High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) [5] was developed in 2013 by the Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC) to replace H.264/Advanced Video Coding (AVC) standard [6], which is the most used video coding standard and has dominated digital video services in the domestic and professional markets for over ten years. In terms of rate-distortion (RD) performance, HEVC roughly doubles the compression performance of H.264/AVC,

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but at a cost of extremely high computational and storage complexities during encoding [12].

The amount of daily data generated in our current interconnected society is astounding. An important amount of this data is transmitted using different video formats. According to the latest Zettabyte Cisco report [3], in 2015, 70% of all IP traffic, both business and consumer, was IP video traffic. Moreover, the trend predicts that this ratio will keep increasing with the market penetration of novel services such as video-on-demand, internet video to TV, virtual reality, 360-degree video or internet-based video surveillance, and existing services such as cloud storage and video streaming services. Moreover, the report also details how all this information will, most likely, be consumed through portable devices, with limited computation and bandwidth capabilities. It is expected that smartphone traffic will double the traffic originated by computers by 2020. Along with the increase in the amount of video information exchanged on the Internet, and the bandwidth and computational limitations of portable devices, there is an increasing demand for higher bit rates, higher video resolutions and better video quality.

This issue results in the need of a new generation of video coding techniques to increase the quality and compression rates of previous standards. Since the release of HEVC, ITU-T Video Coding Expert Group (VCEG) and ISO/IEC Moving Picture Expert Group (MPEG) have been studying the potential need for the standardization of future video coding technologies with a compression capability that significantly exceeds that of the current HEVC standard. To better coordinate this study, VCEG and MPEG created the Joint Video Exploration Team (JVET) as a collaboration framework. The scope of the JVET activity includes the consideration of a variety of video sources and applications. For example, sources include camera-view content, screen content, consumer generated content, virtual reality/360-degree content, and high dynamic range content, while example applications include broadcasting (with live or pre-authored content), real-time video conferencing, video chat, on-demand viewing, storage-based media replay, and surveillance with fixed or moving cameras [8, 11].

These new efforts of standardization and compression enhancements are being explored and implemented by the JVET in a software test model known under the name of Joint Exploration Test Model (JEM) [2]. JEM represents the software model which is being used as a starting point for the next generation of video coding standards following HEVC.

As it has been the case for all past ITU-T and ISO/IEC video coding standards, in HEVC and JEM only the bitstream structure, syntax, constraints and mapping for the generation of decoded pictures are standardized. Consequently, every decoder conforming to the standard will produce the same output for a given standard conformant bitstream. This limitation provides encoder developers with maximum freedom to optimize their implementations and explore new techniques to improve the standard. Moreover, to assist the industry community in learning how to use the standard, the standardization effort not only includes the development of a text specification document, but

also the reference software source code of the encoder and decoder standard implementation. This reference software is usually used as research tool to improve the standard and explore new techniques. For the development of the rate-distortion/complexity analysis detailed in this paper, the reference software for JEM version 3.0 will be used as base encoder. This paper focuses on a comparative evaluation of the quality/computational cost of the HEVC and JEM codecs using objective measures of assessment to analyse their real capabilities. The comparison was performed using the JVET Common Test Conditions presented in [13].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 includes some technical background of the HEVC standard. Section 3 presents the algorithm description of JEM under study, followed by the experimental results in Sect. 4. Finally, Sect. 5 concludes the paper.

2 Technical background

HEVC can be considered an evolution of the current H.264/AVC standard, since it maintains the same hybrid block-based approach used in all previous video compression standards. In addition, new tools have been introduced in HEVC that increase its coding efficiency compared with H.264/AVC [14].

One of the most important changes affects picture partitioning [10]. HEVC defines a new flexible Coding Tree Unit (CTU) structure which is a replacement of the Macroblocks (MBs), 16×16 pixel blocks, used in previous standards. With the aim of achieving an optimal adaptation to the content details, CTUs can vary from a size of 64×64 pixels, to something much smaller, as it can be iteratively partitioned into four square sub-blocks of half resolution, named Coding Units (CUs), with a minimum allowable size of 8×8 pixels. Therefore, a CTU can be further partitioned into four depth levels, from $d = 0$ for 64×64 CU to $d = 3$ for 8×8 CUs, having 4^d CUs in each depth level. Thus, a CU in depth level d can be denoted as $CU_{d,k}$, ($k = 0, 1, \dots, 4^{d-1}$), and the four corresponding sub-CUs as $CU_{d+1,4k+i}$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, 3, k = 0, 1, \dots, 4^{d-1}$). In a CTU of 64×64 , it can be observed that the total number of possible combinations of CUs is $(2^4 + 1)^4 + 1 = 83522$ showing the necessity of reducing the encoder complexity.

HEVC increases even more the flexibility of the CTU by defining two tree structures containing new unit types: the Prediction Units (PUs), and the Transform Units (TUs). For intra-picture prediction, a PU uses the same $2N \times 2N$ size as for the $CU_{d,k}$ to which it belongs, allowing it to be split into four $N \times N$ PUs only for CUs at the minimum depth level. Therefore, the PU size can range from 64×64 to 4×4 pixels. For inter-picture prediction, several non-square rectangular block shapes are available in addition to square ones, allowing eight different PU sizes ($2N \times 2N$, $2N \times N$, $N \times 2N$, $N \times N$, $2N \times nU$, $2N \times nD$, $nL \times 2N$, $nR \times 2N$).

The prediction residue obtained in each of the PUs is transformed using various TU sizes from 32×32 to 4×4 . In Fig. 1, an example of the partitioning

Fig. 1 Partitioning of CTU into CUs, PUs and TUs

Fig. 2 Partitioning of CTU into CUs (white), PUs (green) and TUs (black) applied to the BQSquare sequence

is shown, depicting how a CTU is structured in a hierarchical tree where each CU branch ends in a leaf ($CU_{d,k}$) that is the root for the two new prediction and transform trees. Figure 2 shows the partitioning of CTU into CUs (white), PUs (green) and TUs (black) applied to the BQSquare sequence.

It should be noted that a CU can be divided into different PUs (see Fig. 1), and each of these available PUs has to be evaluated for all intra/inter prediction modes available, and each of the obtained residual blocks can be transformed into up to three TU sizes. HEVC checks most of the PUs (inter and intra modes) to decide whether it should split a CU or not by choosing the best R-D case. Furthermore, in the case of inter prediction, for each of these PU partitions a motion estimation algorithm is called. This wide range of possibilities makes HEVC much more computationally expensive than its predecessor, H.264/AVC. HEVC introduces changes in other modules too, such as intra prediction (where a total of 35 different coding modes can be selected), new image filters or new transform sizes [14], among others. As expected, the

selection of the optimal partitioning for each CU/PU/TU is an intensive time consuming process due to the huge number of combinations that have to be evaluated.

The above analysis evidences the need to reduce the Rate-Distortion Optimization (RDO) complexity for the HEVC intra/inter prediction, in order to make real-time HEVC video codecs with the best possible performance. With the aim of reducing this huge RDO complexity, several suboptimal fast HEVC video codecs have been developed by the industry using a reduced set of prediction modes that are previously selected as candidates, in a low complexity evaluation process.

3 Algorithm description of Joint Exploration Test Model

This section describes the coding features that are under coordinated study by the JVET. They have been included in the JEM test model as potential enhanced video coding technology beyond the capabilities of HEVC.

JEM is being developed on top of HEVC test model (HM version 16.6) [4]. The basic encoding and decoding flowchart of HEVC is kept unchanged in JEM. However, the design elements of the most important modules, including the modules of block structure, intra and inter prediction, residue transform, loop filter and entropy coding, have been modified, introducing new tools. The following new coding features are included in JEM [2]:

- Block structure
 - Quadtree plus binary tree (QTBT) block structure
- Intra prediction improvements
 - 65 intra prediction directions
 - 4-tap interpolation filter for intra prediction
 - Boundary filter applied to other directions in addition to horizontal/vertical
 - Cross-component linear model (CCLM) prediction
 - Position dependent intra prediction combination (PDPC)
 - Adaptive reference sample smoothing
- Inter prediction improvements
 - Sub-PU level motion vector prediction
 - Locally adaptive motion vector resolution (AMVR)
 - 1/16 pel motion vector storage accuracy
 - Overlapped block motion compensation (OBMC)
 - Local illumination compensation (LIC)
 - Affine motion prediction
 - Pattern matched motion vector derivation
 - Bi-directional optical flow (BIO)
- Transform
 - Explicit multiple core transform
 - Mode dependent non-separable secondary transforms
 - Signal dependent transform (SDT)

Fig. 3 Illustration of a QTBT structure

- Adaptive loop filter (ALF)
- Enhanced CABAC design
 - Context model selection for transform coefficient levels
 - Multi-hypothesis probability estimation
 - Initialization for context models

All the methods listed above have been integrated into the main software branch of JEM [7], and in particular, in the software implementation of JEM 3.0.

3.1 Block structure

In JEM, some additional concepts are included to this picture partitioning stage compared to HEVC. JEM incorporates a QuadTree plus Binary Tree (QTBT) structure for blocks. By the use of this structure, the separation in CU, PU and TU is no longer needed. This gives more flexibility for CU partition shapes to better match the local characteristics of the video sequence. Therefore, in JEM, through QTBT, CUs, TUs and PUs have the same block size. In QTBT, CUs can have either square or rectangle shapes like PUs in HEVC. Each CTU (up to 256×256 pixels) is first partitioned by a quadtree structure in squared CUs. Then, leaf nodes can be further partitioned by a binary tree structure. By the use of this tree, each CU can be split in horizontal and vertical CUs, defining the final structure of the CTU and, in consequence, its specific subdivision in CUs. An example of a CTU block structure in JEM is depicted in Fig. 3. We may see how the binary tree determines the type of CU splitting. A value of 1 on the binary structure of the QTBT determines a symmetric vertical split for a CU, while a 0 value specifies a horizontal split. For the quadtree splitting, there is no need to indicate the splitting type since a block is always split horizontally and vertically into 4 sub-blocks with an equal size.

The following parameters are defined to have efficient signalling of a QTBT:

- CTUSize: the root node size of a quadtree, same concept as in HEVC.
- MinQTSIZE: the minimum allowed quadtree leaf node size.
- MaxBTSIZE: the maximum allowed binary tree root node size.
- MaxBTDepth: the maximum allowed binary tree depth.
- MinBTSIZE: the minimum allowed binary tree leaf node size.

In one example of the QTBT partitioning structure, the CTU size is set as 128×128 pixels (for the luma, and in the case of YUV420 subsampling format 64×64 pixels for the chroma), the MinQTSIZE is set to 16×16 , the MaxBTSIZE is set to 64×64 , the MinBTSIZE (for both width and height) is set to 4, and the MaxBTDepth is set to 4. The quadtree partitioning is applied to the CTU

Fig. 4 Proposed 67 intra prediction modes

first to generate quadtree leaf nodes. The quadtree leaf nodes may have a size from 16×16 (i.e. the MinQTSize) to 128×128 (i.e. the CTUSize). If the leaf quadtree node is 128×128 , it will not be further split by the binary tree since the size exceeds the MaxBTSize (i.e. 64×64). Otherwise, the leaf quadtree node could be further partitioned by the binary tree. In this way, the quadtree leaf node is also the root node for the binary tree with a binary tree depth of 0. When the binary tree depth reaches MaxBTDepth (i.e. 4), it implies no further splitting. When the width of the binary tree node equals to MinBTSize (i.e. 4), it implies no further horizontal splitting. Similarly, when the height of the binary tree node equals to MinBTSize , it implies no further vertical splitting. The leaf nodes of the binary tree correspond to CUs that are further processed by the prediction and transform modules without any further partitioning.

3.2 Intra and inter prediction improvements

For intra prediction, to capture finer edge directions presented in natural videos, the directional intra modes are extended from 33, as defined in HEVC, to 65. The new directional modes are depicted as red dotted arrows in Fig. 4. The Planar and DC modes remain the same. These denser directional intra prediction modes apply for all block sizes and both luma and chroma intra predictions. To accommodate the increased number of directional Intra modes, an Intra mode coding method with 6 Most Probable Modes (MPMs) is used. Two major technical aspects are involved: 1) the derivation of 6 MPMs, and 2) entropy coding of 6 MPMs and non-MPM modes.

Regarding inter prediction, with QTBT, each CU can have at most one set of motion information for each prediction direction. Two sub-CU level motion vector prediction methods are studied by splitting a large CU into sub-CUs and deriving motion information for all the sub-CUs of the large CU. Advanced Temporal Motion Vector Prediction (ATMVP) method allows each CU to fetch multiple sets of motion information from multiple blocks smaller than the current CU in the collocated reference picture. In the Spatial-Temporal Motion Vector Prediction (STMVP) method, motion vectors of the sub-CUs are derived recursively by using the temporal motion vector predictor and spatial neighbouring motion vector. As in HEVC, JEM defines the merge mode to copy the motion information from neighbour blocks. In HEVC, motion vector accuracy is one-quarter pel (one-eighth in the case of chroma components for YUV420 video). In JEM, the accuracy for the internal motion vector storage and the merge candidate increases to one-sixteenth pel. The highest motion vector accuracy (1/16 pel) is used in motion compensation inter prediction for the CU coded with Skip/Merge mode

3.3 Other improvements

In JEM, in addition to the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT)-II and the 4×4 Discrete Sine Transform (DST)-VII which have been employed in HEVC for transform coding, an Adaptive Multiple Transform (AMT) scheme has been chosen to encode the inter and intra residual CUs. It uses different transforms from the DCT and DST families than the ones that are used in HEVC. The newly introduced transform matrices are DST-VII, DCT-VIII, DST-I and DCT-V.

In JEM, an Adaptive Loop Filter (ALF) with block based filter adaption is applied. For the luma component, according to the direction and activity of local textures, one among 25 filters is selected for each 2×2 block. ALF aims to reduce visible artifacts such as ringing and blurring by reducing the mean absolute error between the original image and the reconstructed image.

In HEVC, the entropy coder used is Context-based Adaptive Binary Arithmetic Coding (CABAC). JEM uses an enhanced version of CABAC with a modified context modelling for transform coefficients, a multihypothesis probability estimation with context-dependent updating speed, and an adaptive initialization of models.

4 Rate-distortion/complexity analysis

4.1 Encoding parameters

This section aims to evaluate the rate-distortion/complexity capabilities of JEM version 3.0 with respect to HEVC. Our experiments rely on the default configuration of HM 16.6, which is used as an anchor for the obtained results. For a fair comparison, the experiments are conducted with a single-threaded implementation of the encoders. The hardware platform used in the experiments is composed of an Intel® Xeon® E5-2630L v3 CPU running at 1.80 GHz and 16 GB of main memory. To ensure a common framework for the simulations, the experiments were conducted under the Common Test Conditions and Software Reference Configurations recommended by the JVET [13] for the All-Intra (AI), Low-Delay (LD) and Random-Access (RA) mode configurations. That recommendation specifies the use of four Quantization Parameter (QPs) (22, 27, 32 and 37) and a set of 24 test sequences classified in six classes, A1, A2, A, B, C and D, which cover a wide range of resolutions from the largest (4096×2160 pixels) to the smallest (416×240 pixels), and frame rates from 100 fps to 24 fps. All the sequences use YUV420 chroma subsampling and a bit-depth of 10 (A1, A2 and A classes) and 8 bits (B to D classes).

Table 1 Comparison of different versions of JEM with HM 16.6 for RA configuration [9]

JEM version	BD-rate	ETR
JEM 1	-20.84%	5.35×
JEM 2	-22.93%	5.32×
JEM 3	-26.62%	11.32×

Table 2 JEM3.0 compared to HEVC coding performance summary with different configurations [9]

Test configuration	BD-rate			ETR	
	Y	U	V	Enc.	Dec.
All Intra	-18%	-21%	-21%	60×	2×
Random Access	-26%	-30%	-29%	11×	10×
Low Delay B	-21%	-25%	-26%	7×	7×
Low Delay P	-24%	-28%	-29%	6×	4×

4.2 Metrics

The rate-distortion/complexity analysis was evaluated in terms of Encoder Time Ratio (ETR) and R-D performance. The ETR measure was computed following the Equation 1. Regarding the R-D performance, the Bjntegaard Delta Rate (BD-Rate) metric defined by ITU is used [1]. The BD-Rate provides the average difference between the R-D curves measured as a percentage of bit rate that is necessary to increase or decrease to achieve the same Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) quality in both curves. In our simulation, a negative BD-Rate means the encoded bit rate using the JEM codec under study is lower than the bit rate obtained with HM, thus it is denoted as the gain in terms of bit rate saving.

$$ETR(\%) = \frac{Enc.Time(JEM)}{Enc.Time(HM)} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

4.3 Simulation Results

Table 1 shows the performance progress of JEM compared with the HM 16.6 reference software for the RA configuration in terms of BD-rate gain and ETR. It can be observed that JEM codec obtains up to 26% bitrate reduction while increasing the computational complexity by around 11×. The performance of JEM 3.0 compared to the HM reference software is also summarized in terms of encoder time in Table 2 for the AI, LP-P, LD-B and RA mode configurations. A significant increase of computational complexity can be observed for the AI configuration (up to 60×).

Fig. 5 Distribution of encoding time (RA configuration)**Table 3** Profiling results for RA configuration (JEM 3.0)

Class/Sequence	ME_UNLIME	ME_UNLFME	ME_UNLOTH	ME_BLIME	ME_BLFME	ME_BLOTH	ME_OTHER	INTRA_LUMA	INTRA_CHRO	AffineMerge	Merge2Nx2N	MergeFRUC	OTHER
A1 Tango	1.61	5.23	4.89	2.17	3.02	0.32	11.62	21.13	2.17	0.26	18.76	22.68	6.16
Drums100	1.33	3.89	4.00	0.77	2.23	0.26	12.37	16.71	1.62	0.56	27.45	22.72	6.11
CampfireParty	1.32	4.00	5.57	1.94	2.26	0.29	5.98	35.35	5.27	0.09	12.10	20.04	5.79
ToddlerFountain	1.36	2.09	4.22	0.56	1.17	0.20	5.52	41.44	4.33	0.05	17.19	17.17	4.72
A2 CatRobot	1.15	4.60	4.30	1.50	2.70	0.30	13.46	16.19	1.57	1.12	23.72	23.01	6.40
TrafficFlow	0.55	4.57	2.95	0.65	2.64	0.21	14.92	23.42	1.04	0.92	25.28	16.65	6.21
DaylightRoad	1.18	4.39	4.26	1.48	2.56	0.29	12.17	20.03	1.77	1.05	22.78	21.96	6.08
Rollercoaster	1.75	6.10	5.83	2.68	3.46	0.36	11.73	16.26	1.85	1.11	17.83	24.84	6.21
A Traffic	0.55	3.85	3.31	0.69	2.23	0.24	12.59	21.75	0.78	0.46	26.77	21.23	5.58
PeopleOnStreet	1.43	2.88	4.48	0.81	1.62	0.28	9.02	24.25	1.86	0.33	24.43	22.94	5.69
Nebuta	0.60	2.79	2.85	0.50	1.60	0.19	8.53	23.22	2.25	3.49	24.97	22.56	6.47
SteamLocomotive	1.54	5.62	4.63	2.33	3.23	0.31	11.56	22.71	2.14	0.20	17.96	21.83	5.96
B Kimono	1.17	3.93	4.00	1.07	2.27	0.27	11.98	19.22	1.49	0.41	25.21	23.23	5.77
ParkScene	0.80	3.68	3.70	0.96	2.14	0.27	11.96	22.38	1.14	0.31	25.35	21.59	5.73
Cactus	1.10	4.53	4.76	1.68	2.60	0.31	10.67	21.45	1.82	1.01	20.18	23.85	6.09
BasketballDrive	1.43	4.08	5.04	1.62	2.32	0.31	9.64	25.43	2.58	0.51	18.53	22.44	6.08
BQTerrace	0.75	4.95	4.57	1.58	2.85	0.34	13.22	13.80	0.70	0.33	25.63	24.22	7.07
C BasketballDrill	1.37	5.16	6.23	2.40	2.89	0.41	9.44	19.58	1.97	0.38	16.40	27.32	6.48
BQMall	1.22	5.00	5.77	2.29	2.85	0.40	10.69	16.44	1.38	0.40	18.98	28.08	6.51
PartyScene	0.92	3.86	4.98	1.57	2.18	0.36	10.02	18.74	1.36	0.79	21.52	27.46	6.25
RaceHorsesC	1.60	4.36	6.44	2.27	2.45	0.43	7.83	23.49	2.27	0.59	15.45	26.16	6.66
D BasketballPass	1.51	4.40	6.75	2.37	2.46	0.45	8.05	21.80	2.44	0.27	15.53	27.07	6.91
BQSquare	0.59	4.05	4.72	1.35	2.36	0.37	12.95	12.39	0.36	0.88	26.36	26.28	7.37
BlowingBubbles	0.87	4.39	5.59	2.14	2.52	0.42	10.10	15.66	0.92	0.60	19.92	30.02	6.89
RaceHorses	1.55	4.40	6.90	2.50	2.48	0.49	7.99	20.35	1.92	0.54	15.52	28.27	7.10
Class A1	1.40	3.80	4.67	1.36	2.17	0.27	8.87	28.66	3.35	0.24	18.87	20.65	5.70
Class A2	1.16	4.92	4.33	1.58	2.84	0.29	13.07	18.97	1.56	1.05	22.40	21.61	6.22
Class A	1.03	3.78	3.81	1.08	2.17	0.26	10.43	22.98	1.76	1.12	23.53	22.14	5.92
Class B	1.05	4.23	4.41	1.38	2.43	0.30	11.49	20.45	1.54	0.51	22.98	23.06	6.15
Class C	1.28	4.59	5.86	2.13	2.59	0.40	9.50	19.56	1.74	0.54	18.09	27.26	6.47
Class D	1.13	4.31	5.99	2.09	2.45	0.43	9.77	17.55	1.41	0.57	19.33	27.91	7.06
Media	1.17	4.27	4.83	1.59	2.44	0.32	10.56	21.32	1.88	0.66	20.95	23.74	6.25

Figure 5 shows the profiling results of JEM 3.0 obtained for the RA configuration. These timing values have been extracted from the average of all the tested sequences and the four QP values. As can be seen, more than 70% of the encoding time is devoted to the Inter prediction, becoming the most computationally expensive operation in the encoder, whereas 23% of the total execution time corresponds to the Intra prediction. The remaining encoder modules (labelled as “Others”), including transform, quantization, entropy

coding, and in-loop filtering represents only around 6% of the total encoding time. The complexity of the Inter module can be justified by the large amount of repetitive operations that the encoder has to perform on the same picture samples but with different block partitions. Finally, Table 3 shows in detail the JEM profiling results obtained for the RA configuration for all the tested sequences and for different stages of the encoder. It can be observed that the new features of “Merge” operation in JEM represent an expensive operation in the encoder.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents the coding features that are under coordinated test model study by the JVET, and presents a rate-distortion/complexity analysis. Experimental results show that the new model (JEM 3.0) achieves 25% bitrate reduction, but at a cost of an extremely high computational complexity ($11\times$) with respect to HEVC. Future versions of the model should consider encoder complexity as one of the criteria when evaluating the new tools to be included, encouraging further encoder complexity reduction. Moreover, different techniques to accelerate the encoder should be proposed before the new standard is ready to be used in real applications. These techniques might make use of CPU and/or GPU parallelism, as well as other soft computing algorithms.

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